

REAL SENTINEL-2 SUPER-RESOLUTION: THE CASE FOR MISREGISTRATION-AWARE TRAINING DATA

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Abstract—The deployment of single-image super-resolution models for Sentinel-2 imagery is currently hindered by a significant domain gap: models trained on simulated data frequently generate blurred outputs or structural artifacts when applied to real-world acquisitions. This work identifies a critical issue in standard training data simulation protocols as the primary source of this disparity. We demonstrate that conventional down-sampling of spectral bands drastically reduces the magnitude of inherent inter-band misregistration, thereby training models on data that is geometrically cleaner than actual Sentinel-2 products. Consequently, standard deep learning architectures fail to learn robustness to the parallax and temporal offsets present in real L1C and L2A data. To address this, we introduce a progressive simulation framework that explicitly models inter-band geometric shifts, point-spread functions, and noise. We benchmark state-of-the-art methods against the proposed registration-aware graph neural network. Our results show that, while standard models degrade rapidly under complex geometric perturbations, the proposed spectral registration-aware approach, when trained on an exaggerated displacement protocol to enforce geometric learning, successfully reconstructs sharp, high-frequency details in real-world images. These findings establish that modeling geometric inter-band inconsistency is a prerequisite for practical Sentinel-2 super-resolution.

Index Terms—super-resolution, real-world super-resolution, spectral registration, graph neural networks, Sentinel-2

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sentinel-2 mission has established itself as a cornerstone of Earth observation (EO), providing systematic global coverage with high revisit frequency [1]. However, the spatial resolution of 10 m–60 m ground sampling distance (GSD) limits applications requiring fine geometric precision [2, 3]. To mitigate this, single-image super-resolution (SISR) exploits spectral correlations to enhance coarser bands [4, 5]. While deep learning approaches, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [6] and transformers [7], have achieved remarkable performance on simulated benchmarks, their transition to real-world Sentinel-2 imagery is frequently flawed

by significant performance degradation. Models that excel in simulation often produce blurry reconstructions or structural artifacts when applied to actual Sentinel-2 products [8, 9].

We identify that the primary cause of this domain gap lies in the training data simulation protocols for super-resolution (SR) tasks. In the absence of true high-resolution (HR) ground truth for Sentinel-2, the standard practice is to generate simulated training pairs by blurring and downsampling existing images [5, 10]. While computationally convenient, this “naive” downsampling creates a gap between training and inference conditions. Crucially, the operation inadvertently suppresses the sensor’s intrinsic geometric errors. The inter-band misregistration and parallax effects inherent to the Sentinel-2 focal plane, which can manifest as shifts of several pixels depending on the viewing angle and terrain [11, 12], are geometrically compressed by the downsampling factor. Consequently, models trained on such data learn to assume nearly perfect pixel alignment across spectral bands. When deployed on real-world data, where such alignment is physically impossible due to temporal offsets and sensor geometry, these models fail to fuse spectral information effectively, resulting in characteristic “checkerboard” artifacts and loss of detail [13].

In this work, we address this limitation by examining the impact of training data realism on model generalization. Instead of relying solely on standard naive downsampling, we introduce a tiered simulation strategy that generates training sets with increasing levels of geometric complexity. We define three distinct simulation tiers, ranging from ideal alignment to severe misregistration, by explicitly varying sensor-specific parameters, including scale-consistent subpixel shifts, band-dependent point-spread functions (PSFs), and noise. This approach enables us to conduct a robustness stress test on state-of-the-art architectures. We demonstrate that standard baselines, such as DSen2 [5] and hybrid attention transformer (HAT) [14], are highly sensitive to these geometric perturbations. To validate our findings, we evaluate a registration-aware graph neural network (GNN) adapted from the MagNat architecture [15]. Crucially, we adopt a perspective grounded

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in multi-image SR (MISR) principles: rather than treating inter-band geometric shifts solely as noise to be corrected, we exploit them as a source of aliased high-frequency information [16]. By viewing the spectral bands as a sequence of misregistered observations, our approach leverages these subpixel offsets to reconstruct geometric structures that are ambiguous in perfectly aligned data. While the original MagNAt was designed for multi-image fusion, we modify the backbone to decouple geometric alignment from feature extraction in the single-image, multi-band context. By training our GNN on a challenging simulation tier, we encourage robust shift estimation, bridging the domain gap. The GNN resolves high-frequency spatial details while maintaining the spectral coherence that conventional models often fail to preserve.

II. DATA GENERATION STRATEGY

Our primary objective is the simultaneous SR of all Sentinel-2 spectral bands to a uniform HR grid. Specifically, we aim to upsample the native 10 m bands by a factor of $3\times$, the 20 m bands by $6\times$, and the 60 m bands by $18\times$, resulting in a unified spectral cube. While we develop and validate our approach using top-of-atmosphere (L1C) products, the methodology is equally applicable to bottom-of-atmosphere (L2A) data, as the orthorectification and geometric characteristics are consistent across both processing levels [17].

The rationale for this unified upsampling, particularly extending beyond the native 10 m limit, is twofold. First, we exploit *guided SR*: the fine spatial structure preserved in the 10 m bands may serve as a geometric prior to sharpen the coarser 20 m and 60 m channels. Second, and more critically, we leverage MISR principles. We hypothesize that the Sentinel-2 spectral stack acts as a sequence of “misregistered observations.” The subpixel geometric shifts between bands (inherent to the focal plane) imply that each band samples the scene at a slightly different spatial phase. By fusing these shifted observations, it should be possible to recover aliased high-frequency information that is lost in any single aligned image. This theoretical foundation justifies upsampling, even the 10 m bands, beyond their native resolution, as the aggregate information in the misaligned stack potentially exceeds the Nyquist limit of a single channel [18].

Simulation Protocol. To systematically evaluate this hypothesis, we adopt the validation framework established by Wald et al. [10], which relies on the “Change of Scale” property. This protocol posits that if a model accurately reconstructs a known reference from a synthetically degraded input, it should perform equally well on real data. However, we identify a critical limitation in how this protocol is typically applied: standard implementations assume that simple spatial downsampling is sufficient to model the sensor’s degradation. As we demonstrate, this assumption fails for Sentinel-2, where geometric and radiometric anomalies (parallax, noise) are intrinsic to the acquisition. Therefore, while we utilize the Wald protocol to generate training pairs, our primary contribution lies in formulating a degradation model that explicitly violates the “ideal” scale invariance to better approximate the

sensor’s physical reality. We establish the HR reference at 60 m GSD to ensure a pristine ground truth. Using 10 m as the target would require upsampling the native 60 m bands, introducing hallucinated details into the training signal. By selecting the coarsest native resolution as the anchor, we use raw data directly and spatially integrate finer bands via area-based resampling, preserving radiometric consistency without interpolation artifacts.

To generate the corresponding low-resolution (LR) training inputs, we simulate the sensor’s degradation process relative to this 60 m anchor. To preserve relative spatial ratios (10:20:60) while targeting the defined upsampling factors, we generate simulated LR inputs at 180 m (10 m bands, $\times 3$), 360 m (20 m bands, $\times 6$), and 1080 m (60 m bands, $\times 18$). Although coarse, these resolutions enable training on the exact scaling relationships required for the target application.

Degradation Model. Standard degradation models typically ignore geometric nuances. However, the physical reality of Sentinel-2 is complex. While European Space Agency specifications require inter-band registration of < 0.3 pixels, this holds only for static scenes. In reality, temporal offsets (up to 2.5 s) induce significant parallax shifts [11, 19]. We define our degradation model for band b as:

$$I_{LR}^{(b)} = \mathcal{D}_s \left((I_{HR}^{(b)} * k_\sigma) \circ \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{v}_b) \right) + \eta(I), \quad (1)$$

where k_σ is the PSF, $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{v}_b)$ applies a geometric shift, and \mathcal{D}_s is downsampling ($s \in \{3, 6, 18\}$). Crucially, $\eta(I)$ represents a physically-motivated Poisson-Gaussian noise model [20], simulating both photon shot noise and electronic read noise to approximate the real, signal-dependent noise characteristics of Sentinel-2 data.

We validate our approach across three distinct simulation tiers. Tier 1 (T1) represents the idealized SISR baseline, assuming perfect alignment ($\mathbf{v}_b = \mathbf{0}$) and zero noise. Tier 2 (T2) introduces realistic Poisson-Gaussian noise and independent shifts of $\mathbf{v}_b \sim \mathcal{U}(-3, 3)$ pixels; for 10 m bands, this models nominal subpixel sensor micro-vibrations. Finally, Tier 3 (T3) employs exaggerated misalignments where $\mathbf{v}_b \sim \mathcal{U}(-9, 9)$ (up to ± 3 LR pixels). While exceeding nominal values, this exaggeration forces the network to abandon pixel-aligned assumptions and explicitly learn to fuse spatially disjoint spectral features.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To effectively exploit misregistered spectral information, we propose a hybrid architecture combining the geometric flexibility of GNNs with the efficiency of CNNs. Our design adapts the MagNAt framework [15], originally developed for MISR, to the single-image multi-band domain. The pipeline operates in three stages: shift estimation, graph-based structural fusion, and guided spectral sharpening.

1. Inter-Band Registration. We begin by adapting the RegNet module from MagNAt to estimate the geometric relationships between spectral bands. While the original implementation aligned temporal acquisitions, we repurpose it to predict the global shift vector \mathbf{v}_b for each spectral band relative

to a reference anchor. This reference may be any band, but in this work we used band B08. This lightweight CNN head operates on the coarse inputs to determine the subpixel offsets inherent to the focal plane, providing the geometric metadata required for graph construction.

2. GNN Backbone: Latent Guide Synthesis. With the shifts estimated, we proceed to structural fusion. Unlike standard CNNs that require fixed grid alignment, our GNN treats every pixel from the native-resolution input bands as an independent node in a continuous spatial domain. We construct a dynamic graph where edges connect input pixels to target HR coordinates based on spatial proximity, explicitly incorporating the predicted shifts \mathbf{v}_b into the distance metric. The GNN aggregates features from these spatially distributed neighbors to synthesize a single-channel, high-resolution *latent intensity map*. This map acts as a “virtual panchromatic band,” capturing the high-frequency structural details recovered from the aliased, multi-band inputs.

3. CNN Module: Guided Sharpening. In the final stage, this GNN-generated structural guide serves as the input to a set of sequential residual CNN blocks. This module functions as a guided upsampler (similar to pansharpening): it propagates the high-frequency geometric details from the latent guide onto the spectrally rich—but spatially coarse—input bands, producing the final super-resolved spectral cube at the target resolution.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

We evaluate the proposed model against two baselines: DSen2 [5] and HAT [14]. We train distinct versions of each model on the three simulation tiers (T1, T2, T3) described in Section II. To ensure a fair comparison, all models were trained until convergence using an early stopping strategy with a patience of 20 epochs, selecting the checkpoint with the lowest validation loss.

For both DSen2 and HAT, input bands are bicubically upsampled to 10 m GSD before processing due to architectural constraints. Additionally, DSen2 outputs are interpolated to the target 3.3 m grid, as it is natively restricted to producing images at 10 m GSD.

B. Quantitative Analysis on Simulated Data

We first quantify performance on the held-out simulated test sets. Table I summarizes the results which highlight a crucial distinction in how architectures handle misregistration in the input data. Transitioning from the idealized T1 to

TABLE I
QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON (PSNR / SSIM) ON THE SIMULATION TIERS. BEST RESULTS ARE BOLDDED.

Model	Tier 1		Tier 2		Tier 3	
	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM
Bicubic	39.78	0.892	38.26	0.877	36.11	0.848
DSen2	42.46	0.929	38.93	0.916	39.36	0.902
HAT	43.13	0.945	43.21	0.950	41.78	0.936
Ours	42.75	0.939	43.58	0.948	43.30	0.946

Fig. 1. Impact of training data difficulty. DSen2 and HAT models degrade when trained on high misalignment (Tier 3), while Ours requires it to learn robust registration.

the subpixel-shifted T2, both HAT and our model achieve performance gains (e.g., Ours +0.83 dB). This confirms that both architectures can leverage subpixel aliasing to enhance resolution. In contrast, DSen2 treats these shifts as noise, causing a performance collapse. However, as shifts increase to the exaggerated magnitudes of T3, the limitation of implicit registration becomes apparent. HAT suffers a significant drop (−1.43 dB) as the shifts exceed its effective receptive field alignment. Our registration-aware GNN, conversely, proves robust; it maintains high fidelity (43.30 dB), effectively managing these large geometric distortions. This demonstrates that while subpixel shifts are beneficial for flexible models, explicit registration is required to robustly exploit the larger displacements that may occur locally in dynamic Sentinel-2 scenes. Notably, this robustness is achieved efficiently: our GNN utilizes ≈ 1.5 M parameters compared to HAT’s ~ 20 M. This $> 10\times$ reduction demonstrates that explicitly modeling physical sensor constraints is far more effective than relying on the brute-force capacity of large transformers to implicitly learn geometric invariance.

C. Real-World Qualitative Analysis

We tested the performance of all architecture variants on real Sentinel-2 L1C scenes. This revealed a divergence in how models react to training data difficulty.

Impact of Training Data. DSen2 and HAT, when trained on the idealized T1 dataset, paradoxically produce the most visually pleasing results on real data. When exposed to the high-displacement training regime (T3), these architectures fail to learn robust registration, resulting in geometric warping and severe blur (see Fig. 1).

Our model exhibits the inverse trend. The variant trained on T2 data produces artifacts; the shifts are too subtle to forcefully

Fig. 2. Qualitative comparison of the best model variants on real Sentinel-2 L1C scenes. To visualize performance across the full spectral range, we display a composite mosaic: the image is divided into spatial patches, where each patch renders a different band combination.

penalize misalignment, leading the GNN to behave like a standard CNN. However, the model trained on T3 effectively activates its registration mechanism. Despite T3 shifts being exaggerated compared to the real L1C input, this training regime grants the model the robustness required to handle the smaller, but physically complex, real-world parallaxes. Consequently, further analysis compares the best-performing version of each architecture: DSen2 (T1), HAT (T1), and Ours (T3).

Structural Stability vs. Artifacts. Visual comparison of band mosaics (Fig. 2) highlights distinct behaviors. DSen2 produces highly stable and spectrally consistent results; however, due to its reliance on bicubic interpolation for 10m bands, the output remains overly smooth, failing to recover high-frequency textures. HAT achieves the highest peak sharpness, often resolving very fine textures, but at the cost of frequent, inconsistent artifacts. We observe band-specific failure modes (e.g., aliasing in one channel, checkerboards in another), leading to spectral decoherence. Our model delivers a balance of resolution and stability. By using a unified latent guide, it enforces a “structural lock” across the spectral stack, recovering details comparable to HAT with significantly fewer artifacts. Crucially, the geometry is consistent across all bands, avoiding the random independent errors seen in the transformer.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated the domain gap hindering the deployment of SISR models on real-world Sentinel-2 imagery. We demonstrated that the widely used “naive” downsampling protocol for creating training data artificially simplifies the

sensor’s geometric reality. While this simplification serves as a necessary precondition for standard CNN and Transformer architectures to function, allowing them to synthesize textures by assuming perfect alignment, it ultimately prevents them from learning to disentangle the physical misregistrations inherent to the platform.

Our benchmarking reveals a critical architectural divergence. Standard models, which excel at texture synthesis on idealized data, treat geometric shifts as noise. Consequently, their performance collapses under complex training conditions, and they exhibit spectral decoherence on real-world inputs. In contrast, our proposed registration-aware GNN effectively transforms these inter-band misalignments from a corrupting noise source into a useful signal for spatial fusion. This comes with a trade-off: while our physics-aware approach may produce softer textures than a hallucinating Transformer, it guarantees the spectral structural consistency required for rigorous EO tasks.

Finally, we identify opportunities to further refine the simulation realism. Our current approach models band-to-band shifts as independent random vectors. However, in reality, these displacements are governed by the fixed arrangement of spectral stripes on the focal plane and the satellite’s orbital motion. Future work will therefore focus on constraining these shifts to a deterministic trajectory based on the specific temporal delays between band acquisitions. Additionally, we aim to extend our graph formalism to estimate dense, pixel-wise flow fields, moving beyond global registration to correct the local parallax effects caused by terrain relief.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Drusch, U. Del Bello, S. Carlier, O. Colin, V. Fernandez, F. Gascon, B. Hoersch, C. Isola, P. Laberinti, P. Martimort, A. Meygret, F. Spoto, O. Sy, F. Marchese, and P. Bargellini, "Sentinel-2: ESA's optical high-resolution mission for gmes operational services," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 120, pp. 25–36, 2012, the Sentinel Missions - New Opportunities for Science. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0034425712000636>
- [2] M. Pesaresi, G. Huadong, X. Blaes, D. Ehrlich, S. Ferri, L. Gueguen, M. Halkia, M. Kauffmann, T. Kemper, L. Lu, M. A. Marin-Herrera, G. K. Ouzounis, M. Scavazon, P. Soille, V. Syrris, and L. Zanchetta, "A global human settlement layer from optical HR/VHR RS data: Concept and first results," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 2102–2131, 2013.
- [3] M. Immitzer, F. Vuolo, and C. Atzberger, "First experience with Sentinel-2 data for crop and tree species classifications in central europe," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/8/3/166>
- [4] L. Liebel and M. Körner, "Single-image super resolution for multispectral remote sensing data using convolutional neural networks," *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. XLI-B3, pp. 883–890, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://isprs-archives.copernicus.org/articles/XLI-B3/883/2016/>
- [5] C. Lanaras, J. Bioucas-Dias, S. Galliani, E. Baltsavias, and K. Schindler, "Super-resolution of Sentinel-2 images: Learning a globally applicable deep neural network," *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 146, pp. 305–319, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0924271618302636>
- [6] Y. Zhang, Y. Tian, Y. Kong, B. Zhong, and Y. Fu, "Residual dense network for image super-resolution," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2018.
- [7] J. Liang, J. Cao, G. Sun, K. Zhang, L. Van Gool, and R. Timofte, "SwinIR: Image restoration using swin transformer," pp. 1833–1844, 2021.
- [8] X. Wang, J. Yi, J. Guo, Y. Song, J. Lyu, J. Xu, W. Yan, J. Zhao, Q. Cai, and H. Min, "A review of image super-resolution approaches based on deep learning and applications in remote sensing," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 21, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/14/21/5423>
- [9] M. Kawulok, T. Tarasiewicz, J. Nalepa, D. Tyrna, and D. Kostrzewa, "Deep learning for multiple-image super-resolution of sentinel-2 data," in *2021 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium IGARSS*, 2021, pp. 3885–3888.
- [10] L. Wald, T. Ranchin, and M. Mangolini, "Fusion of satellite images of different spatial resolutions: Assessing the quality of resulting images," *Photogrammetric Engineering and Remote Sensing*, vol. 63, pp. 691–699, 11 1997.
- [11] F. Gascon, C. Bouzinac, O. Thépaut, M. Jung, B. Francesconi, J. Louis, V. Lonjou, B. Lafrance, S. Massera, A. Gaudel-Vacaresse, F. Languille, B. Alhammoud, F. Viallefont, B. Pflug, J. Bieniarz, S. Clerc, L. Pessiot, T. Trémas, E. Cadau, R. De Bonis, C. Isola, P. Martimort, and V. Fernandez, "Copernicus Sentinel-2A calibration and products validation status," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 9, no. 6, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/9/6/584>
- [12] L. Yan, D. Roy, Z. Li, H. Zhang, and H. Huang, "Sentinel-2A multi-temporal misregistration characterization and an orbit-based sub-pixel registration methodology," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 215, pp. 495–506, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0034425718301792>
- [13] M. Kawulok, T. Tarasiewicz, J. Nalepa, D. Tyrna, and D. Kostrzewa, "Deep learning for multiple-image super-resolution of Sentinel-2 data," in *Proc. IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)*, 2021, pp. 3885–3888.
- [14] X. Chen, X. Wang, J. Zhou, Y. Qiao, and C. Dong, "Activating more pixels in image super-resolution transformer," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, June 2023, pp. 22 367–22 377.
- [15] T. Tarasiewicz and M. Kawulok, "A graph attention network for real-world multi-image super-resolution," *Information Fusion*, vol. 124, p. 103325, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1566253525003987>
- [16] S. Farsiu, M. Robinson, M. Elad, and P. Milanfar, "Fast and robust multiframe super resolution," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 1327–1344, 2004.
- [17] J. M. B. Louis, V. Debaecker, B. Pflug, M. Main-Knorn, J. Bieniarz, U. Mueller-Wilm, E. Cadau, and F. Gascon, "Sentinel-2 SEN2COR: L2A Processor for Users," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:114110450>
- [18] R. Y. Tsai and T. S. Huang, "Multiframe image restoration and registration," 1984. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:59796060>
- [19] ESA Mission Performance Centre, "Data quality report for Sentinel-2 L1C MSI," European Space Agency, Report OMPC.CS.DQR.001.12-2024, January 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sentwiki.copernicus.eu/>
- [20] A. Foi, M. Trimeche, V. Katkovnik, and K. Egiazarian, "Practical Poissonian-Gaussian noise modeling and fitting for single-image raw-data," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 17, no. 10, p. 1737–1754, Oct. 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2008.2001399>